

Supplementary Figure

Hippocampus

Supplementary Figure 1. Difference scores of hippocampal IL-13 in females and males following immune challenge of LPS. Significant interaction between ethanol (EtOH) exposure, choline supplementation, and sex in IL-13 (* $p < 0.05$). Decreases in different scores of **(A)** IL-13 in females and **(B)** IL-13 in males exposed to ethanol compared to non-exposed controls (* $p < 0.01$) which are mitigated by choline supplementation. $n = 10-11$ per group.